

METHODOLOGICAL-DIDACTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF DEVELOPING LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS THROUGH ARTISTIC LITERATURE

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Abstract. *Competency-based model of developing students' linguistic skills through fiction is important in the teaching process. Such a model helps students to develop excellent language competences, as well as develop their critical thinking and creative abilities. Through the competency-based model, students can not only learn the rules of languages and theoretical concepts, but also improve their ability to analyze and understand literary texts. In this way, they can be introduced to creative and original paths to knowledge.*

Keywords: *structural skills, dimensions of competence, structural knowledge, voluntary training.*

Introduction

Literary didactics, as well as general science didactics, aim not only to define individual competencies as educational goals, but also to develop comprehensive competency-based models. Such models are important for the teaching process using literary texts, because they allow to systematically describe the expected learning outcomes and give an option about "What are the ways to achieve knowledge". The analysis of scientific research in the field shows that two main axes are important in the development of competence, and on the other hand, dimensions of competence. In his research, Y.Ossner examines competence, standard and tasks with special attention and examines the relationship between them. Because these concepts are the basic concepts of the current education policy.

Structure of competence, standard and educational task interaction

Competencies described in this image "consist of abilities and skills that individuals have or have learned to solve specific problems, as well as to apply them effectively and responsibly in various situations, it includes the motivation, will and social preparation and skills needed to apply". Competencies can be norm-based, in which case they define educational goals expected in society. But they can also be described empirically, that is, they show what my students can actually do. This only describe the situation at the specified time. Therefore, in general writing competence as an educational goal is possible.

Competencies typically have varying degrees of specificity, and each competence has its own characteristics. For example, general writing competence encompasses the ability to conceptually structure texts, write orthographically correctly, and do so in a successful and general readable manner. It is noted that it is possible to show work with artistic texts as a subject area for competency-based models in the sources that cover the components of the competency-based model of developing students' linguistic skills by means of literary literature. Comprehension of text is considered a core competency-based content in this area. Competency-based content can be defined by sub-competencies, which in turn can be differentiated by level steps. Competency-based dimensions define the type of knowledge (required for structural competencies). Using

terms from educational psychology, (1) declarative knowledge (substantive knowledge), (2) procedural knowledge (practical knowledge/skills), and (3) metacognitive knowledge (knowledge needed to plan, examine, and evaluate work processes) are different from each other. In the guide published by the Council of Europe on the evaluation of language knowledge based on the competency-based approach, we can see that the term "persönlichkeitsbezogene Kompetenz" is used instead of the term metacognitive knowledge. In particular, "competencies consist of a set of (declarative) knowledge, (procedural) skills and personal competencies that enable a person to perform their own "actions".

When we look at the terminological sources of the field, declarative knowledge is understood as knowledge about facts (for example, knowledge about grammatical rules or knowledge about things that are specific to a particular culture or what the rules of etiquette are in a certain society). This is explicit knowledge that can be expressed, described and spoken by the student.

Procedural abilities (sometimes called "procedural knowledge") are abilities that are partially or fully automated, that is, learned (eg, applying grammatical rules often automatically or acting in accordance with certain societal rules and values). Because this is more implicit (i.e. hidden) knowledge, it can only be readily brought to consciousness to a limited extent and rarely expressed. Personal competence is defined as "the sum of personal characteristics, character and attitudes". This includes, for example, cultural attitudes, motivation to learn a language, as well as stable personality factors (such as introversion or self-confidence). In accordance with the central importance of understanding the text and its definition as a competence, it is necessary to develop a competency-based model with the content of understanding the text for working with artistic texts. In theory, it would be possible to avoid breaking this content and identify common measures of text comprehension. However, at least since the publication of the PISA Reading Competency-based Model in 2001, the need to distinguish between the structural competencies of reading comprehension has been mentioned. It is discussed which structural competencies should be acquired for understanding literary texts and whether or not levels should be differentiated within structural competencies. In literary studies, as well as in linguistics and foreign language teaching methods, it can be observed that the understanding of texts includes at least two activities in addition to "basic" reading (that is, understanding each word and sentence). It is necessary to distinguish them from each other: to know the elements of the text and to interpret them. In a number of sources where this topic is covered, we can see that the model of double understanding of texts is studied separately in classes where fiction materials are used, as well as in literature classes; (1) identifying text elements and their interrelationships and (2) interpreting them. These can be summarized as text comprehension competence. They are filled with emotional connection to the text (eg, empathy) and imagination. The model is considered "familiar" for teachers and students: it is widely used in literature classes as an analysis and interpretation competence aimed at identifying and interpreting text elements and structures. Also, this model serves as a basis for the tasks set for educational standards and new teaching aids. However, the level steps in structural competencies are not yet clearly defined. Because of this, it is noted that the comprehension results to be realized in them depend on the level of difficulty of the text.

Although the issue of identifying text elements in field sources has not yet been fully studied, it is noted that it can be described as follows; the reader understands the tendentious objective meaning of the text by identifying (central) text elements and their interrelationships.

This meaning is often not understood by reading the text verbatim, but it must be "inferred" by the reader: He identifies and connects different textual information and fills it with linguistic or even worldly knowledge and experience. But this meaning-making is a 'reconstruction of existing meaning', which is ideally done equally by all 'competent' learners (in the same culture) and can therefore be considered 'objective'. Here, K. Weimar defines the main comprehension result as follows: "Students determine what is "clear" in the text or what can be "defined" by working on the text. When things are encountered that are not "clear" or "expected not to be clear," they are interpreted.' It is clear from the analysis of the available literature that no clear scientific conclusions have yet been formed regarding the ability to understand this "accuracy". In particular, this process has been named differently by scientists as deciphering/re-encryption, understanding, as well as reading comprehension or forming coherence (connections). Based on this, in our research, we call this process "identification of central text elements and their interrelationships".

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